

MANTIQIY ELEMENTLAR ICHIDAN MULTIPLEKSOR VA DEMULTIPLEKSORLARNI TADQIQ ETISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mantiqiy element bazasini yaratishda Elektronik Workbench dasturidan foydalanilgan. Mantiqiy elementlarni hosil qilish davomida elektronik Workbench dasturining imkoniyatlari hamda asosiy funktsiya va buyruqlari keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektronik Workbench, dastur kodi, dasturlash tili interfeysi, demultipleksor.

Annotation: This article uses the Electronic Workbench program to create a logical element database. During the creation of logical elements, the capabilities of the electronic Workbench program and the main functions and commands are mentioned.

Keywords: Electronic Workbench, program code, programming language interface, demultiplexer.

Demultipleksor bajaradigan amalga teskari amalni bajaradi, ya'ni ma'lumotlarni bitta kirish yo'lidan chiqish yo'llarining biriga uzatadi. Demultipleksor bitta informasion kirishga, n adresli shinalarga va $m = 2^n$ - chiqishga ega. Belgilanishi CD (1- m).

Elementlarni modellashtirish uchun fayllar Lab_2_4\Modeli papkada joylashgan.

$$Y_0 \square A_0 \square X; Y_1 \square A_0 \square X.$$

1- rasm. DMX(1-2) demultipleksori, fayl L2_DMX_01.ewb.

Agar X o‘chirgich mantiqiy nolga doimiy ulangan bo‘lsa, deshifrador – demultipleksor (2-rasm) deshifrador sifatida ishlaydi. X informasion kirishga ikkili kod yuqoridagi o‘chirgich yordamida uzatilganda, qurilma demultipleksor vazifasini bajaradi.

2-rasm. Deshifrador – demultipleksor (2-4), fayl L2_DMx_03.ewb.

Multipleksor deb bir necha kirish yo‘llaridan birini tanlab uni o‘zining chiqish yo‘liga ulovchi uzalgga aytiladi. Multipleksor axborot kirish yo‘llariga (D_0, D_1, \dots), adres kirish yo‘llariga (A_0, A_1, \dots), ruxsat signali beriladigan kirish yo‘liga (C) va bitta chiqish yo‘liga (Q) ega (3-rasm).

3- rasm. Multipleksor axborot kirish yo‘llari.

Multipleksor – X axborotni A adres kodiga mos F bitta chiqishga bir necha manbalardan ma‘lumotlarni boshqariladigan uzatuvchi kombinasion raqamli qurilmadir. Multipleksor n adresli shinaga, $m = 2^n$ – chiqishga va bitta F axborotli chiqishga ega. $MUX(m-1)$ belgilanishi.

Masalan, $MUX(4-1)$: kodga bog‘liq holda A_0, A_1 adresli shinagauzatilayotgan

$X_0 \dots X_3$ axborotli kirishlarning bittasi F chiqish kanaliga ulanadi(3-rasm).

$$F = A_1 \bar{A}_0 X_0 + A_1 A_0 X_1 + \bar{A}_1 \bar{A}_0 X_2 + \bar{A}_1 A_0 X_3.$$

4-rasm. MUX(8-1) multipleksor, L2_MUX_02.ewb fayli

Multipleksorlar EI hal qiluvchi kirishga ega, agar unga mantiqiy bir berilsa, unda axborot uzatilishi sodir bo‘ladi. 4-rasmda bu kirish inverslidir. Multipleksorlarda ixtiyoriy mantiqiy funksiyani amalga oshirish mumkin. Masalan, mantiqiy 3 VA (4-rasm) elementini olish uchun, haqiqiylik jadvali tuziladi(1-jadval).

“VA” elementining haqiqiylik jadvali

1-jadval

5- rasm. MUX(8-1) multipleksorga asoslangan 3VA mantiqiy element, L2_MUX_03.ewb fayli

Misol. MUX(4-1) da F funksiyani amalga oshirish:

$$F = D_0D_1D_2 + D_0D_1 + D_2 + D_0D_1D_2 + D_0 + D_1 + D_2$$

Operatsiyalar ketma-ketligi:

X o'zgaruvchiga qaraganda, adresli kirishlar kichik. D_0 va D_1 to'g'ri va inversli ko'rinishdagi hamma qo'shiluvchilar kirgani uchun, $D_0 = A_0$; $D_1 = A_1$ deb qabul qilamiz.

6-rasm. Multipleksorni sxematik belgisi

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, ushbu maqolada mantiqiy elementlar ichidan multipleksor hamda demultipleksorlarni tadqiq etildi. Bunday tadqiq etish davomida bir nechta uskuna va buyruqlardan, funksiyalardan foydalanildi. Buning natijasida tadqiqot natijalari olindi va formulalar yordamida ular hisoblab, ko'rib chiqildi.

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